

FORMATION OF THE FUNDAMENTALS OF INFORMATION CULTURE IN CADETS OF HIGHER MILITARY EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS THROUGH MODERN TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. The article discusses the basics of forming the information culture of cadets through the use of modern educational technologies.

key words: cadet, information culture, technology, educator, higher military educational institution.

Over the past decades, society has undergone fundamental changes in its understanding of the goals of education and ways to implement them. From the recognition of knowledge, abilities and skills as the main results of education, there has been a transition to an understanding of learning as a process of preparing students for real life, readiness to take an active position, successfully solve life problems, be able to cooperate and work in a group.

Our world is unthinkable without a constant uncontrolled flow of various types of information, which a person must be able to process, analyze and be able to apply in his work.

The developed ability to code and organize information support for any type of activity characterizes one of the facets of culture – information.

In modern society, information becomes extremely important and the more knowledge, skills and abilities we have in this area, the more we are valued as specialists and workers.

Information culture is an active process that accompanies us throughout our lives. Pursuing this goal, we begin to develop and form an information culture among future officers - cadets of higher military educational institutions.

Many scientists understand the term “information culture” as a confident command of information flows, its analysis and application in order to achieve a certain result [2, p. 88].

An analysis of the literature and best practices in the field of psychological and pedagogical science strongly confirms that young men are especially sensitive to the formation of an information culture. This is confirmed by several factors: the rapid pace of development of the intellectual level, which is a characteristic feature of this age period; features of the development of the ability to cognitive activity that manifest themselves during adolescence; constant improvement of psychophysical abilities, which contributes to more effective assimilation of information.

In today's reality, there are quite a lot of proven technologies and those that are on the verge of innovation. But their main essence is that they are reproducible, effective and scientifically sound.

Considering the world pedagogical experience, we can confidently say that the use of technology called “mind map” in organized educational activities contributes to the development of the foundations and further development of information culture among future officers [4].

Mind mapping is an innovative method of storing information that is both easy to use and unique in its approach. with the ability to stimulate and develop creative thought processes, as well as improve speech skills, it is an indispensable tool for developing children's intelligence and creative thinking.

The method of their application is based on the visual-figurative thinking of the individual, which is fundamental in adolescence.

The formation of the foundations of information culture is facilitated by the "scribbling" technology [5].

Scribbling is a technique of laying out images on a canvas that represents encoded information. while listening to a certain melody or text, the student selects the picture or text he needs and tries to reproduce the intended plot.

Another technology is the technology of project activities.

The technology of project activities is based on the implementation of projects of various directions. the most important thing in this technology is to help the student deepen their knowledge in the chosen research topic, but also to develop their skill in finding the necessary information [5].

Thus, we can conclude that the issue of developing the information culture of future officers remains relevant and in demand today. this age is the most favorable for the development of many psychophysical qualities of an individual, as this is scientifically proven and justified.

A well-formed information culture gives the cadet the opportunity to easily explore the world around him and is characterized by easy receipt, perception and further practical use of the information received in his daily activities. all of the above modern technologies help the teacher not only to introduce diversity into the educational process, but also to purposefully solve problems in forming the foundations of information culture among cadets of higher military educational institutions

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